

The Correspondence Principle and the Idea of Balanced Reactions

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In bound state quantum mechanics, high energy eigenvalues are said to lead to a density $W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, whose envelope approaches the classical value $1/v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity given by $\sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$. For the quantum oscillator, the ground state mimics classical statistical mechanics, while the high energy states mimic classical mechanics. For both classical statistical mechanics and classical physics, we argue in this note that one may use a reaction picture to derive probabilities. Traditionally, the classical density $1/v(x)$ is obtained from $dx = v dt$ or $dx/v = dt$ with “dt” being proportional to probability. In classical statistical mechanics, one has two particle scattering and imposes a balance using $P(p1)P(p2)=P(p3)P(p4)$. In the case of $V(x)$, one may also write a reaction equation (1) showing particles leaving and entering a little box. In this note, it we argue it would be good to have a consistent picture when dealing with densities, namely a reaction picture, with “breakup or decay” balancing “synthesis”. We then try to argue that such a reaction picture may actually also apply to high energy eigenvalue quantum mechanical bound states.

Reaction Picture in Classical Statistical Mechanics

The reaction picture is perhaps most clearly seen in classical statistical mechanics. Particles in a liquid evaporate (decay), but new particles from the vapour are added (synthesis) and there is a balance. For two particle scattering in a gase, one has an “and” probability condition for each reaction which is balanced under time reversal:

$$P(p1)P(p2)=P(p3)P(p4) \quad ((1))$$

Taking the natural log of ((1)) yields a conservation type equation which may be compared with a conservation of kinetic energy for elastic scattering. This in turn leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for p momentum. In (1), it has been shown that at a point x in a system with a potential $V(x)$, one does not only have the decay-synthesis reaction ((1)), but also particles entering and leaving under the influence of $V(x)$. We also describe this as a decay-synthesis reaction and argue that a balance leads to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$.

Reaction Picture in Classical Mechanics

The spatial density in classical mechanics $1/v(x)$ is given by setting $dt=dx/v$ proportional to probability. One argues that the amount of time spent in a tiny unit dx represents the probability. Fast particles spend very little time and so have a low probability. It seems that this “thinking” is different from the concept of decay-synthesis balance which we wish to introduce here. Consider many classical ensembles. One is told that there is a probability for a particle to be at x by “looking” for a particle at this point in each member of the ensemble. If a particle is found

$n(x)$ times out of N , then one has probability $=n(x)/N$ without a concept of time. Next, consider $P(x)$ and $P(x+dx)$. $P(x)$ does not change in time, so if it decays (i.e. a particle leaves), there must be a balancing synthesis (a particle must arrive). Now, a particle leaves dx in a time $dt=dx/v$. $1/dt$ can be thought of as a reaction rate, so v/dx is this rate. Here dx is a constant. If one uses:

$$P(x) v(x)/dx = P(x+dx)v(x+dx)/dx = \text{constant} \quad ((2))$$

then one has a balance and $P(x)=C/v(x)$ is a solution. One may argue that nothing new has been done here, but we wish to formulate the problem in terms of decay and synthesis so that this approach can be used consistently in classical mechanics, statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics.

Quantum Mechanics

As a specific example, consider the quantum oscillator. For all energy levels, one has wavefunctions of the form of a Hermite polynomial times $\exp(-ax^2)$, a being a constant. This is oscillatory and as energy increases, one expects very rapid oscillations with an envelope approaching $1/v(x)$ if the Bohr correspondence principle is to hold. (Similarly, a sine wave for a particle in a box with no potential achieves a very high frequency and the envelope looks like a straight line i.e. $1/v$ where v is now a constant.) Thus, quantum mechanics is very different from classical mechanics, even in the high energy limit, as there are these numerous oscillations. Nevertheless, the envelope approaches $1/v(x)$ accurately.

In (2), the authors calculate the envelope in the following manner. They take the quantum density in the form of a Hermite polynomial squared times $\exp(-a2x^2)$. Here a is a constant. They then take the Fourier transform, obtaining a Laguerre polynomial, and next obtain the high n limit. They essentially lead to a J_0 Bessel function $J_0(px_0/h)$ where p is momentum x_0 is the amplitude and h the Planck constant, plus a complicated series with a very small weight as n approaches infinity. They then take the inverse Fourier transform and the J_0 Bessel function takes the form of $1/v(x)$ with $.5mv(x)v(x) + .5k x^2 = E = .5k x_0^2$. Thus, the Fourier transform of the J_0 Bessel function seems to be yielding the “envelope function” of the quantum density which is a highly oscillatory function composed of the square of a Hermite polynomial and $\exp(-2ax^2)$.

In general, it seems that one takes the Hilbert transform to obtain an envelope of a function, but in (3) it is shown that $F[H(u)(w)] = - \text{sgn}(w) F(u) w$ where F is the Fourier transform, H the Hilbert transform, u the function and w the argument and $\text{sgn}(w)$ is the signum function. This seems to be similar to the approach taken in (2) to obtain the “envelope function”

Quantum Mechanics in terms of a Reaction and the Correspondence Principle

We wish now to suggest it might be possible to consider a high energy eigenvalue bound state problem in terms of a reaction (decay-synthesis balance). We first note, however, that one does not need to approach high energy eigenvalues to see classical values. They seem to be present in quantum mechanics for all energy levels. For example:

$$(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) = \text{classical kinetic energy} \quad ((3))$$

And

$$(-1/2m) d/dx \{ [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) \} = -d/dx V(x) \quad ((4))$$

Consider now a quantum wavefunction. It is often highly oscillatory, sometimes at low energy eigenvalues with the frequency increasing at high energy values. For low energy values, one can also create an “envelope”, but the peaks are so far apart that it seems to be somewhat meaningless. For a high frequency, one tends to only see the peaks (a matter of resolution perhaps) and so focuses on the “envelope function”. Consider now a wavefunction $W(x)$ with a high frequency of peaks. The correspondence with classical physics seems to only be with these peaks as one approaches the highest possible energy eigenvalues. Consider two consecutive peaks, one at x_1 and the other at x_2 with probabilities $W(x_1)W(x_1)$ and $W(x_2)W(x_2)$. The wavefunction itself seems to be a long time average of plane wave states scattering off of a potential. The change in the density is given by:

$$d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x) d/dx W(x) + [d/dx W(x)][d/dx W(x)] + W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x) + \dots \quad ((5))$$

One may think of the change in density as an average value measured over a long period of time. This amount of time is the same for each point x . The first term already has the form of a flux or average of momentum i.e.

$$(1/W) dW/dx = (1/W) \text{Sum over } p \quad \hbar p \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

Thus $d/dx W^*W$ seems to be like a decay rate at x_1 and a synthesis rate at x_2 . For $dW/dx = 0$, ((5)) becomes:

$$d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x) = C W(x)W(x) v(x)v(x) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, it is proportional to classical kinetic energy. This holds for all energy levels, but we have argued that an envelope does not really make sense for low frequencies of oscillations.

If one writes a balance equation:

$$P(x_1) \text{ Decay Rate } (x_1) = P(x_2) \text{ Synthesis Rate} \quad ((8))$$

$$W(x_1)W(x_1) v(x_1)v(x_1) = \text{a similar form at } x_2 = \text{constant} \quad ((9))$$

Thus, a solution is $W(x)W(x) = 1/v(x)$ which matches the classical density.

This should hold for any bound wavefunction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue in this note that a decay-synthesis balance approach may apply to both the classical density $1/v(x)$ and the quantum density for high energy eigenvalues. If one is able to use such arguments, there seems to be some consistency between establishing probabilities in classical, classical statistical and quantum mechanics. This may be useful when comparing the different approaches. It seems to be somewhat confusing to use dt (a small interval of time) as a measure of probability for a classical system and then a balance reaction for a statistical system.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Time Reversal Balances and the Effect of Flux in Statistical and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Bernal, J., Martin-Ruiz, Alberto, Garcia-Melgarejo, J. A Simple Mathematical Formulation of the Correspondence Principle 2018 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1101.1242.pdf>
3. Hilbert Transform https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hilbert_transform